

METABOLISM AND THEIR INTERDEPENDENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7420886>

Abstract: The search for early markers of atherosclerosis is an effective method for providing personalized medicine allowing the prevention of the progression of this pathology. The aim of this study was the determination of the total indices of dyslipidemia and the identification of the gender indices of the extended lipid profile in the population of residents of the Southern and Central Federal Districts (Voronezh, Belgorod, Lipetsk, Kursk and Rostov regions) for the identification of early markers of atherogenicity. In a simultaneous clinical study, involving 339 patients (mean age 48 years), the concentrations of total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL (low density lipoproteins), HDL (high density lipoproteins), apolipoproteins B and A1, the ApoB/ApoA1 ratio and the atherogenic coefficient were determined. For the identification of the relationship between changes in lipid profile indicators with cytotoxicity syndrome and indicators of carbohydrate metabolism, the activity of ALAT (alanine aminotransferase), GGTP (gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase) and glucose content were also studied. Analysis of the results of the lipid spectrum of the population sample of the middle age group revealed significant metabolic disorders of lipid metabolism with a predominance of atherogenic lipid fractions and a significant excess of indicators of atherogenic lipid fractions in middle-aged men in comparison with women. It has been shown that the apoB/apoA1 index can be used as an auxiliary marker for early assessment of the prevalence of atherogenic lipid fractions, allowing the identification of risk groups for the development of diseases associated with metabolic disorders.

Keywords: Lipid metabolism, Atherosclerosis, Metabolic syndrome, Cholesterol, Triglycerides, LDL, HDL, ApoB / ApoA1, Atherogenic coefficient

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) associated with atherosclerosis represent a global medical and social problem and are the main cause of mortality and disability in the population [1]. The PESA study showed that worldwide 71 % of middle-aged men and 43 % of women have signs of subclinical atherosclerosis [2], mortality from CVD in the Russian Federation in 2017 amounted to 587.6 cases per 100 thousand population [3, 4]. The concept of high cardiovascular risk is associated primarily with dyslipidemia due to an increase in the concentration of atherogenic lipids. Under normal conditions, insulin limits

lipolysis, however, with the development of insulin resistance it is unable to suppress this process [5].

The production of very-low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) and triglycerides in the liver and their retention in tissues increases with the development of insulin resistance and dyslipidemia is formed [6]. The nosological spectrum of diseases associated with dyslipidemia, has a similar pathogenesis, determined by laboratory markers of the disease: metabolic syndrome; obesity; diseases of the biliary tract and liver; steatohepatitis; arterial hypertension; hypothyroidism and adrenal gland pathology, thromboembolism, COVID-19. The studies using PCSK9 inhibitors [4] and the results of the ODYSSEY OUTCOMES study with alirocumab [5] have shown that lowering LDL cholesterol decreases the incidence of cardiovascular heart disease [4, 5]. Although LDL is recognized as the main source of intracellular lipid accumulation in plaque, native LDL does not induce significant lipid accumulation in cultured cells. The modification of LDL, which changes the physicochemical characteristics of the particles is atherogenic [6]. During the course of its modification, the LDL particle is first desialylated, followed by an increase in the particle density, a decrease in size, and the acquisition of a negative charge [6]. Modified LDL is utilized mainly by the non-specific phagocytosis, which leads to the accumulation of intracellular cholesterol and the formation of foam cells [1].

Foam cells are an important structural component of atherosclerotic plaque, and modified LDL forms immune complexes that have a damaging effect on the vascular wall, narrowing the vessel lumen and promoting thrombus formation [1]. Despite the leading role of LDL in the development of CVD, associated with atherosclerosis, the role of other lipoproteins, in particular apolipoprotein B (apoB), which is the main component of LDL was demonstrated [2]. It has been shown that the concentration of apoB can be considered a direct indicator of the total amount of atherogenic lipoproteins in the bloodstream [1]. The largest studies, INTERHEART [22] and AMORIS [3], showed that the determination of the levels of apoB and apoA1 in blood plasma seems to be the most informative indicator of the risk of developing CVD [4]. Previously, the main role in the development of atherosclerosis was attributed to hypercholesterolemia, but recent clinical studies showed the participation of any hyperlipidemia in the onset and further development of atherosclerosis [6].

Thus, it was shown that although triglyceride levels above 1.7 mM/l are a factor of increased risk of CVD, the positive effect of lowering triglycerides has not been confirmed by evidencebased medicine [5]. The leading “pacemaker” of the

pathological process and the degree of functional abnormalities which is not always determined by functional and visual diagnostic methods, are determined based on the presence and combination of biochemical abnormalities [2]. The role of dyslipidemic disorders in the etiopathogenesis of CVD, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, non-alcoholic steatohepatosis, diseases of the biliary tract, menopausal disorders determine the relevance of the search for early markers for predicting the risk of dyslipidemia in men and women [1]. Possible methods to search for biomarkers are:

1. In-depth/extended study of the lipid profile.
2. Inclusion in the analysis of new markers characterizing the functioning of the main metabolic systems and their disorders, which are involved in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis in addition to the traditional factors of cardiovascular risk [3].

For the identification of the specificity and predictive value of apolipoproteins apoA1 and apoB in comparison with cholesterol, HDL, LDL, and triglycerides we decided to analyse the extended lipid spectrum during the stage of transition of women to menopause and the indicators of men of a similar age group in order to determine the basic risks of development of atherogenic dyslipidemia. This approach determines the resources of health during the formative stage of risks associated with age, regardless of hormonal changes. The aim of this study was the determination of the total indices of dyslipidemia and the identification of the gender indices of the extended lipid profile in the population of residents of the Southern and Central Federal Districts (Voronezh, Belgorod, Lipetsk, Kursk and Rostov regions) in order to search for early markers of atherogenicity.

In the group of patients with normal TG, an increase in glucose content was detected in 21.6 % (mean value – 7.43 mM/l, reference value – up to 6.2 mM/l), while in the group of patients with elevated TG an increase in glucose was more significant (mean value – 8.44 mM/l) and was detected in 42.3 % of patients (Fig. 11). This correlation reflects the need for the ABC strategy proposed by the National Diabetes Education Program: diabetologists and patients with diabetes should pay attention not only to the control of glycemia (“A” - HbA1c) and blood pressure (“B” - blood pressure), but also to the level of blood lipids (“C” - cholesterol) [4].

The main cause of hypertriglyceridemia in diabetes mellitus is the low sensitivity of visceral adipose tissue to the anti-lipolytic action of insulin, which leads to increased lipolysis, the entry of large amounts of free fatty acids into the portal bloodstream and, in combination with hyperinsulinemia, an increase in

the synthesis of triglycerides and VLDL by the liver. In addition, in patients with type 2 diabetes with hyperglycemia, the activity of endothelial lipoprotein lipase, which is responsible for the catabolism of triglycerides and VLDL, is reduced, which aggravates this disorder.

Thus, as a result of the conducted studies of lipid metabolism indicators in middle-aged group (from 32 to 61 years) of Southern and Central Federal Districts of Russia (Voronezh, Belgorod, Lipetsk, Kursk and Rostov regions) the following distinguishing features were identified:

- significant metabolic disorders of lipid metabolism in the middle age group with a predominance of atherogenic lipid fractions, which can serve as a negative indicator of the health status of the working-age population;
- in the absence of a universal marker of lipid atherogenicity for the early diagnosis of pathological changes in the body, a comprehensive screening of LDL fractions, triglycerides, glucose indicators for the isolation of risk groups in relation to the development of metabolic disorders leading to the development of atherogenic vascular lesions is justified. The feasibility of determination of insulin, conducting a glucose tolerance test, C-peptide is determined by the specialists in order to clarify the basic diagnosis, and their results do not always correlate with the severity of atherogenic changes;
- the results of the study showed that the apoB/apoA1 ratio can be used as an auxiliary marker for the early assessment of the prevalence of atherogenic lipid fractions, allowing to identify risk groups for the development of diseases associated with metabolic disorders;
- the revealed significant excess of atherogenic lipid fractions in men of the middle age group in comparison with women, at the stage of addition of natural menopausal changes in lipid metabolism, determines an almost two-fold increase in the risks of developing cardiovascular lesions in men in the age category up to 50 years;
- the revealed correlation of the TG level and the increase in glucose content shows the need for constant monitoring of the blood lipid profile in patients with diabetes;
- screening detection of indicators of hypertriglyceridemia and/or dyslipidemia, even in the absence of a somatic pathology, should be an indication for in-depth clinical and laboratory examination: exclusion of organic lesions of parenchymal organs (primarily of the liver and biliary tract). Author contributions Mittova V. O.

– writing text; research design development. Khoroshikh A. O. – analysis of scientific literature, bibliography design. Zemchenkova O. V. – preparation and revision of the research part of the text. Ryazantsev S. V. - experimental research, data collection and analysis. Maslov O. V. – development of methodology, data processing. Corzh E. V. – interpretation of data, final conclusions, preparation of a literature review. RyasnayaLokinskaya L. S. – writing of the clinical part of the discussion of the results, analysis of scientific literature. Alabovsky V. V. – scientific leadership, research concept.

References:

1. Mc Namara K., Alzubaidi H., Jackson J. K. Cardiovascular disease as a leading cause of death: how are pharmacists getting involved? *Integrated Pharmacy Research and Practice*. 2019; 8: 1–11. [https:// doi.org/10.2147/IPRP.S133088](https://doi.org/10.2147/IPRP.S133088)
2. Fernández-Friera L., Peñalvo J. L., FernándezOrtiz A., Ibañez B., López-Melgar B., Laclaustra M., Oliva B., Mocoora A., Mendiguren J., Martínez de Vega V., García L., Molina J., Sánchez-González J., Guzmán G., Alonso-Farto J. C., Guallar E., Civeira F., Sillesen H., Pocock S., Ordovás J. M., Sanz G., JiménezBorreguero L. J., Fuster V. Prevalence, vascular distribution, and multiterritorial extent of subclinical atherosclerosis in a middle-aged cohort: the PESA (Progression of Early Subclinical Atherosclerosis) study. *Circulation*. 2015;131: 2104–2113. [https:// doi/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.114.014310](https://doi/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.114.014310)
3. Strategiya razvitiya zdravookhraneniya v Rossiiskoi Federatsii na period do 2025 goda. Ukaz Prezidenta Rossiiskoi Federatsii ot 06 iyunya 2019 g. No254. [Healthcare development strategy in the Russian Federation for the period until 2025. Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of June 6, 2019 No. 254.]. Moscow, 2019. (In Russ.)
4. Poznyak A., Orekhov A. N., Grechko A. V., Poggio P., Myasoedova V. A., Alfieri V. The Diabetes Mellitus–Atherosclerosis Connection: The role of lipid and glucose metabolism and chronic inflammation. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2020;21(5): 1835. <https://doi/10.3390/ijms21051835>
5. Diagnostika i korrektsiya lipidnogo obmena s tsel'yu profilaktiki i lecheniya ateroskleroza. Rossiiskie rekomendatsii, VI peresmotr, M; 2017. 44 s. [Diagnosis and correction of lipid metabolism with the aim of prediction and treatment of atherosclerosis, Russian recommendations, VI revision, M; 2017. 44 p.] (In Russ.)
6. Faintuch J., Faintuch S. *Obesity and DiabetesScientific Advances and Best Practice*, 2nd Edition. Springer; 2020. 994 p. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53370-0>